

Understanding Product Appearance: Cognitive and Emotional Response to Product Visual Form

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Abstract

Consumer response to product appearance is presented as one stage in a process of communication between designers and consumers. The product is considered to be the medium through which this communication takes place. Consumers' psychological responses to product form are comprised of emotional and cognitive aspects, with cognitive response comprising aesthetic, semantic and symbolic components. Taken in turn, these components relate to the perception of beauty, interpretation of what the product 'says about itself' and judgements on what the product 'says about its user'. These three aspects of cognitive response are often considered in isolation. However, remaining cognisant of each component promotes consideration of the way in which each component interacts with the others. Emotional responses to products may be better understood by considering the aesthetic, semantic and symbolic responses that accompany them. This paper discusses consumer response to product visual form within the context of an integrated conceptual framework and suggests implications for future research.

Keywords: product aesthetics, product semantics, social symbolism, product design, styling.

Introduction

The visual appearance of products is a critical determinant of consumer response and product success. Judgements are often made on the elegance, functionality and social significance of products based largely on visual information (Crilly, Moultrie, and Clarkson 2004). These judgements relate to the perceived attributes of products and frequently centre on the satisfaction of consumer wants and desires, rather than their needs. As such, consumers make inferences on the possible experience of usage or ownership based on product appearance. Consequently, emotional response to products is influenced by an understanding of product appearance. However, the existing theories relating to product appearance have not previously been integrated to form a general and coherent perspective. This hinders understanding of how product appearance influences the emotions anticipated by consumers. This paper seeks to address this gap, by synthesising the contributions of a number of authors from a variety of fields. A categorisation of cognitive response to product appearance is

presented that comprises aesthetic, semantic and symbolic components. Thus, a structure is provided upon which consideration of the emotional expectations of consumers may be based.

Products as a medium of communication

In general, consumers have no access to the designers of the products they interact with. Thus, the consumers' interpretation of the design is based predominantly on their interaction with the product (Norman 1988). Designers only communicate attributes such as elegance, functionality, mode-of-use and social significance through the medium of the product. This semiotic perspective on product design focuses on viewing products as signs capable of representation (Vihma 1995). If products are to be considered as signs that are interpreted by users it is useful to consider consumer response to product appearance as one stage in a process of communication (Coates 2003; Krippendorff and Butter 1984; Monö 1997). Shannon described a basic system of communication as comprising five elements: source, transmitter, channel, receiver and destination. The information source produces a message which is encoded into a signal and transmitted across a channel. The receiver decodes the signal and the message arrives at the destination (Shannon 1948).

Monö has applied this basic model of communication to the study of product design (Monö 1997). Here, the producer of the product is responsible for design and manufacture. The designer, or the design team, may be viewed as the source of the message. The product itself may be regarded as the transmitter of the message, and the environment in which the consumer interacts with the product may be regarded as the channel. The consumer is involved in both the perception of products and subsequent response. Consequently, the consumer's perceptual senses may be regarded as the receiver of the design message and their faculty for response may be regarded as the destination (see Figure 1).

The orthodox view of consumer behaviour presents response to products as comprising cognition and affect, which are followed by behaviour (Bloch 1995; O'Shaughnessy 1992). Norman describes both affect and cognition as information processing systems, where the cognitive system makes sense of the world and the affective system is judgmental (Norman 2002). Each system influences the other, with cognition leading to affect, and affect influencing cognition (Ashby, Isen, and Turken 1999; Coates 2003; Norman 2002). A

consumer's psychological response (comprising cognition and affect) influences the way in which they behave towards the product (Bloch 1995). Marketers frequently use the terms approach or avoid to distinguish between the behavioural responses of an interested and disinterested consumer (Bloch 1995). Thus, cognitive response to products influences both affective response and subsequent behaviour.

Figure 1, Basic framework for products as a medium of communication.

Cognitive Response

Cognitive response refers to the judgements that users or consumers make about products based on the information perceived by the senses. These judgements include evaluation of the products' perceived qualities. In the existing literature, a number of different approaches are taken to describe response to design. However, when reviewing the work of Crozier (1994), Cupchik (1999), Lewalski (1988), Baxter (1995) and Norman (2004) strong precedent emerges for using the following three categories to describe cognitive response to product appearance: aesthetic impression, semantic interpretation and symbolic association.

- Aesthetic Impression may be defined as the sensation that results from the perception of attractiveness (or unattractiveness) in products. This is related to Crozier's "response to form", Cupchik's "sensory/aesthetic response", Lewalski's visual "X-values" (which express "the order of visual forms"), Baxter's "intrinsic attractiveness" and Norman's "visceral level" in design.
- Semantic Interpretation may be defined as what a product is seen to say about its function, mode-of-use and qualities. This is related to Crozier's "response to function", Cupchik's "cognitive/behavioural response", Lewalski's visual "Y-values" (which are "conductive to

purposefulness and functionality”), Baxter’s “semantic attractiveness” and Norman’s “behavioural level” in design.

- Symbolic Association may be defined as the perception of what a product says about its owner or user: the personal and social significance attached to the design. This is related to Crozier’s “response to meaning”, Cupchik’s “personal/symbolic response”, Lewalski’s visual “Z-values” (which “fulfil the need to belong and for self esteem”), Baxter’s “symbolic attractiveness” and Norman’s “reflective level” in design.

These elements of cognitive response to product appearance may lead to expectation of a variety of emotional (affective) responses. Recently, Desmet (2003) has proposed five categories for the emotional responses that products may elicit: instrumental, aesthetic, social, surprise and interest. Instrumental emotions (such as disappointment or satisfaction) stem from perceptions of whether a product will assist the user in achieving their objectives. Aesthetic emotions (such as disgust or attraction) relate to the potential for products to delight and offend our senses. Social emotions (such as indignation or admiration) result from the extent to which products are seen to comply with socially determined standards. Surprise emotions (such as amazement) are driven by the perception of novelty in a design. Finally, interest emotions (such as boredom or fascination) are elicited by the perception of challenge combined with promise.

Each of these categories of emotion result from an appraisal of the product. With regard to visual perception, this appraisal is based on the aesthetic impressions, semantic interpretations and symbolic associations that comprise cognitive response. However, whilst aesthetic emotions are directly related to aesthetic impressions, in general, the full range of cognitive responses may contribute to the full range of affective responses. For example, instrumental emotions may result from aesthetic impressions, semantic interpretations and symbolic associations if the product is seen to promise the satisfaction of decorative, practical and social objectives.

The aesthetic impressions, semantic interpretations and symbolic associations that comprise cognitive response to product appearance are described in detail below. Following this, plans for future work are discussed before conclusions are drawn.

Aesthetic impression

People may look at products and find them visually attractive, elegant or beautiful (Coates 2003). Often the activity of perceiving objects is pleasurable in itself, irrespective of other value judgements that might be made (Berlyne 1974). This positive aesthetic impression has interested design researchers for decades (Palmer 1996; Pye 1978) and philosophers and art theorists for centuries before them (Crawford 1974; Csikszentmihalyi and Robinson 1990). Although the subject of beauty has been studied for centuries there is still no unanimous consensus on what is beautiful or what comprises beautiful artefacts (Routio 2002). Furthermore, there has been little progress in the formulation of a “coherent theory with respect to the aesthetic aspect of design” (Veryzer 1995: 641). Despite this, there are aesthetic principles and theories that provide a useful conceptual foundation. Product attractiveness may be considered as comprising objective and subjective components and as a balance between opposing factors, as described below.

The relative importance of the objective and subjective aspects of aesthetic experience have been debated for centuries. Most early scholars of beauty held the perspective that attractive features resided in the object itself (Routio 2002). Beauty was considered to be an objective property of the stimuli under consideration. Certain lines, proportions, shapes and colours were believed to be inherently attractive (Arnheim 1992). This approach suggests that each object will have an ideal form, which once attained will tend to be considered attractive by everyone (Coates 2003). However, Crozier suggests that “the presence of demonstrable differences between peoples’ judgements makes it difficult to believe in universal aesthetic principles [and that] inherent responses [may be] a mirage” (Crozier 1994: 46-47). He suggests that the visual appeal of objects is also influenced by socio-cultural, socio-economic, historical and technological factors. As such, the ideals and standards to which one culture aspires may not be appreciated by other cultures.

In addition, aesthetic experience has been described as resulting from a balance of opposing factors, such as interest and understanding. Gombrich proposed that “aesthetic delight lies somewhere between boredom and confusion” (Gombrich 1984: 9). For stimuli to be considered attractive, the extent to which they make sense to the viewer must be balanced by the extent to which they present something of interest. Berlyne suggests that the hedonic value (pleasure) associated with perception of a stimulus will peak when there is an optimum

level of psychological arousal; too little arousal will result in indifference whilst too much will result in displeasure (Berlyne 1974).

More recently, Coates has united these perspectives by suggesting that aesthetic impression is based not only on a balance of interest and understanding but that it is also influenced by a combination of objective and subjective factors (Coates 2003). He describes positive aesthetic impression as the result of a balance between two opposing factors: information and concinnity. Information relates to both novelty and contrast, which may serve to arouse a consumer's interest. Conversely, concinnity relates to the order and sense perceived in a design, which may assist the consumer in understanding the product. Coates suggests that the information and concinnity perceived in a product stem from not only the objective qualities of the product itself, but also from the subjective experiences of the consumer. Thus, the information and concinnity perceived in a product may be divided into their objective and subjective components.

- Objective information may be regarded as the amount of contrast that a design presents against its background and within itself. This is determined by the way in which certain design elements are combined. For example, products which are of a strikingly different colour to the environment in which they are perceived and which utilise a variety of lines, shapes and textures will exhibit a high degree of contrast.
- Subjective information may be regarded as the novelty perceived in the design. This is largely determined by the extent to which the product deviates from forms with which the consumer is already familiar. For example, products utilising shapes and lines that are a radical departure from those normally encountered arouse interest due to their novelty.
- Objective concinnity may be regarded as the order perceived in the design. This is determined by the application of design principles such as the Gestalt Rules (Baxter 1995; Köhler 1930). For example, products exhibiting a high degree of symmetry and orthogonality appear simple, rational and ordered.
- Subjective concinnity may be regarded as the extent to which the design appears to make sense to the viewer. This is determined by the consumer's personal, cultural and visual

experiences that assist them in understanding the product. For example, products that use design cues from other products, or exhibit a good degree of commonality with existing designs are often easy to comprehend.

Coates conceptualises these four aesthetic ingredients as items on a weighing scale. The total information (comprising objective and subjective components) is on one side and the total concinnity (also comprising objective and subjective components) is on the other. If information outweighs concinnity the product will be considered confusing, meaningless and ugly. Alternatively, if concinnity outweighs information, the product will be considered simple, dull and boring. Coates suggests that only when information and concinnity balance, and the product is at once engaging and comprehensible, will it be considered attractive.

Semantic interpretation

Designed objects are often functional devices that operate in some way to perform the task for which they are used (Avital 1992). Consequently, a significant portion of the value assigned to products may be attributed to their utility. This may comprise practical qualities such as function, performance, efficiency and ergonomics. These aspects of utility can be conveyed to some extent by the visual form of the product. This evaluation of a design's apparent utility and perceived qualities is described here as semantic interpretation.

The definition of product semantics relevant to this interpretation is limited to what the product appears to communicate about itself. The extent to which products are seen to reflect the identity of their owners is discussed separately in the section on symbolic association. A distinction is made here between what the product is seen to indicate about itself and what it is seen to symbolise about its owner (Gotzsch 2000). Consequently, a narrower definition of product semantics is adopted than that proposed by Krippendorff and Butter, who included symbolic qualities such as “the personalities a [car] driver seeks to acquire by owning a particular model”(Krippendorff and Butter 1984: 4). Instead, a treatment of product semantics is explored which is more congruent with Monö's semantic functions (Monö 1997).

Monö's book, *Design for Product Understanding*, presents a comprehensive guide to semantic interpretation from a semiotic perspective. Monö states that a product's visual form

may appear to communicate its practical qualities through four semantic functions: description, expression, exhortation and identification (Monö 1997):

- Description refers to the way in which the outward appearance of a product presents its purpose, mode-of-operation and mode-of-use. For example, a grooved handle may suggest the direction in which it is to be turned and indicate how much force will be required. From a product's description, consumers may infer the practical benefits the product will offer and how they must interact with it.
- Expression refers to the properties that the product appears to exhibit. For example, modifications to a product's visual form may alter the consumer's interpretation of qualities such as density, stability or fragility. The properties that a design expresses may assist the consumer in understanding how the object should be treated.
- Exhortation refers to the requests or demands that a product appears to make of those perceiving it. For example, flashing switches may request that they be switched off. Through exhortation the product may elicit the appropriate actions from the user for correct and safe operation.
- Identification principally refers to the extent that the origin and affiliation of a product are conveyed. For example, the manufacturer, product type, product range and specific model may be communicated by text, graphics and design cues. The identification of a product assists the user in understanding the category to which the product belongs.

Monö suggests that, in application, the distinction between these semantic functions may not always be clear. The communication of a specific attribute may be shared across semantic functions. For example, the product's purpose may be described by the physical form and identified by the addition of text labels and graphics (Monö 1997).

Symbolic association

In addition to their apparent decorative and practical qualities almost all products are seen to hold some socially determined symbolic meaning (Doyle 1999; Levy 1959; Mayall 1979). As

such, products may evoke associations which one links to the commodity, or assumes that others must associate with it (Haug 1986). This culturally agreed meaning of objects allows a person to communicate their identity through products; it allows them to “project a desirable image to others, to express social status and to make visible their personal characteristics” (Dittmar 1992: 89). Thus, products contribute to the expressive equipment with which people present themselves (Goffman 1990).

Whereas semantic interpretation relates to what the product is seen to indicate about itself, symbolic association is determined by what the product is seen to symbolise about its user, or the socio-cultural context of use (Gotzsch 2000). For example, whilst a chair denotes (or affords) sitting, a throne connotes (or implies) status and power (Muller 2001). As such, the social value assigned to products determines the symbolic associations that are made.

Products are used by people to communicate their identity not only to others, but also to themselves (Dittmar 1992). The objects we consume both reflect and contribute to who we are and as such, “we regard possessions as parts of ourselves” (Belk 1988: 139). In addition to this distinction between an inward and outward expression of identity, Dittmar divides the symbolic qualities associated with products into self-expressive and categorical meanings (Dittmar 1992).

- The self-expressive symbolism associated with products allows the expression of unique aspects of one’s personality. This includes individual qualities, values and attributes (Dittmar 1992). These self-expressive meanings serve to differentiate the consumer from those that surround them (Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton 1981). As such, products are used to reflect the owner’s distinction from others, they represent a means of defining one’s self as unique and may be used to symbolise a person’s unique identity” (Snyder and Fromkin 1980).
- The categorical symbolism associated with products allows the expression of group membership, including social position and status (Dittmar 1992). These categorical meanings serve to integrate the consumer with those that surround them (Csikszentmihalyi and Rochberg-Halton 1981). Indeed, one of the principal approaches to expressing membership of a social group is through shared consumption symbols (Belk 1988).

The symbolic meanings attached to products are culturally defined (Dittmar 1992). Therefore, the extent to which a product is seen to reflect or support identity will be determined by the cultural context within which the product is consumed.

Aesthetic, semantic and symbolic interaction

Cognitive response to product visual form has been described as comprising aesthetic impressions, semantic interpretations and symbolic associations. However these aspects of response do not operate independently, but are highly inter-related with each one influencing the others.

Firstly, the visual appeal of a design is influenced by the extent to which it makes sense to the viewer. One contributor to this concinnity is the apparent agency (or usefulness) of the object (Coates 2003). Thus, a consumer's aesthetic impression is influenced by their semantic interpretation of the product. Secondly, there is not necessarily a clear distinction between the symbolic value associated with a product and semantic interpretation of its instrumental (or utilitarian) value. Qualities such as the apparent power of a machine may be transferred to its user, who may be perceived as being strong and capable themselves (Dittmar 1992). Thus, the semantic expression interpreted in a design, which defines its character, may also be of symbolic significance in reflecting the character of its owner or user. Finally, connections may be observed between the perceived aesthetic and symbolic qualities of objects. The aesthetic judgements that consumers make often reflect their taste; products hold a symbolic value in reflecting the social groups to which consumers belong (Bourdieu 1984). Thus, when products are consumed, expressions of "I like that" may be implicitly converted to "I'm like that" (Postrel 2003: 101-103); taste is not only a matter of aesthetic preference, but also of social discrimination (Bayley 2000).

Detailed descriptions have been given of aesthetic, semantic and symbolic responses along with general descriptions of affective and behavioural responses. Combining these perspectives with the basic communication framework (see Figure 1) provides a coherent and integrated framework for the subject of product appearance (see Figure 2).

Figure 2, Product communication framework showing response to product appearance.

Summary

There is a broad range of literature available offering insight into the subject of response to product appearance. This literature has been reviewed including contributions from significant texts that are seldom referenced. In particular, aesthetic, semantic and symbolic responses (which are usually discussed separately) have been drawn together. This provides an opportunity to consider the way in which these aspects of response influence each other and how their relative importance might vary depending on context. These aspects of cognitive response have been considered in relation to the accompanying affective and behavioural responses that consumers experience and exhibit. Furthermore, consumer response has been discussed within the context of a general framework of communication (see Figure 2).

Future work

The development of an integrated framework for understanding cognitive response to product appearance indicates several potential future research questions. For example, during the design process, how conscious are designers of consumer response? To what extent do practising designers intend products to evoke specific responses and how best might these intentions be categorised? Furthermore, what processes are used to convert these intentions into product form? Finally, do consumers tend to perceive products in the ways that designers anticipate?

A series of interviews is being conducted with practising industrial designers who are providing valuable insights into the questions outlined above. Information is being gathered on the way in which designers use a product's visual form to express product qualities, to evoke emotions and to influence consumer behaviour. However, if products are to be considered as a medium of communication between designers and consumers then there are clearly opportunities for breakdowns in communication to occur. This raises the question of what discrepancies exist between the consumer responses that designers intend and the actual responses that consumers experience. It is hoped that further research into designer intent and consumer response will identify what these problems in communication are, what they are caused by and how they might be alleviated.

Conclusions

Product appearance plays a significant role in determining consumer response. It may provide for unarticulated consumer requirements and suggest product qualities that are otherwise difficult to ascertain. Judgements on whether a product is attractive include not only consideration of whether the product looks good, but also whether it appears functional and says the right things about the owner. As such, product appearance influences consumers' expectations of their emotional engagement with products. Remaining cognizant of the aesthetic, semantic and symbolic aspects of response, and conceptualising them as part of the framework presented, will assist any further attempts to understand consumer response to product appearance.

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